

Policy Recommendations for Enhancing Employees' Job Performance Based on Structural Equation Model: A Case Study of Commercial Banks in Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: The banking system wants to develop quickly, sustainably, and meet digitalisation requirements, so it needs a team of highly qualified staff. Moreover, employee career competency is one of the most critical issues for organisations, helping them maintain a competitive position in the market.

Objective: The research aimed to measure critical factors influencing employees' job performance at commercial banks in Vietnam. Besides, the authors propose management implications for improving employees' career competency and job performance in the banking sector in the era of digital banking development in Vietnam.

Methodology: This study applied a structural equation model consisting of five factors: knowledge, attitude, hard skills, soft skills, and technology, and examined the impact of the above factors on tasks, context, and job performance. Data were collected from 900 employees working in 40 branches of 15 commercial banks in Vietnam. The analyses were done using SPSS 20.0 and Amos software.

Result: After testing the scale's reliability, convergence, and discrimination, the study's results showed that the critical factors of knowledge, attitude, skills, and technology positively impact task, contextual, and job performance.

Conclusion: Based on the results of testing the research model, the authors provided empirical evidence that the career competency framework includes critical factors: knowledge, attitude, skills, and technology that positively impact task performance, contextual performance, and employee job performance.

Unique Contribution: This study provides evidence on the factors that influence employees' job performance in commercial banks in Vietnam.

Key Recommendation: Managers should take the issue of employees performance seriously by taking into account factors like attitude, skills, and technology.

Keywords: Career competency, task, contextual, job performance, technology, commercial bank

Introduction

Human resource management is an integral part of organisation and management, making a necessary contribution to the development and success of the bank. Effective human resource management will help banks ensure sufficient qualified human resources and appropriate capabilities to implement business goals, create a positive working environment, and support employees in developing themselves and making maximum contributions to the organization. This also helps banks to establish sustainability in the current context. Currently, the issue of human resource management is a serious concern and is of interest to banks because it dramatically impacts their sustainable development (Luo et al., 2021; Sypniewska et al., 2023). Human resource management in banking activities includes planning, recruitment, utilisation, training, development, job performance evaluation, and human resource compensation, specifically, career competency. Career competencies can significantly affect job performance in the banking industry. According to research, the professional competencies of banking industry employees directly and positively impact job satisfaction and the results. Another study found a relationship between career competencies and job performance in the banking industry.

Kisekka and Goel (2023) showed that the aspects of professional competence developed and measured in previous studies have not been consistent. Besides, most previous studies in Vietnam focused on building a competency framework in specific occupations or job positions. The assessment of career adaptability and the level of job completion do not consider the correlation between the competency framework and output work results, especially in the banking sector (Abukhalifa & Kamil, 2022). Therefore, this can be regarded as one of the few studies on this issue based on the characteristics of commercial banks in Vietnam. It is expected to contribute to the theoretical basis and serve as a foundation for further finance and banking research.

In short, career competencies, which refer to an individual's knowledge, skills, and abilities, play a vital role in the banking industry's success. This helps employees perform their tasks effectively and improves work outcomes such as increased productivity, customer satisfaction, and profits (Ng et al., 2024). These findings highlight the importance of investing in employee training and development programs to enhance the banking industry's career competencies, and the authors' motivation to implement this study. Based on the banking industry practice and the above analysis, the study aims to measure critical factors influencing employees' job performance at commercial banks in Vietnam. Finally, the authors propose management implications for career competency and job performance of employees in the banking sector in the era of digital banking development in Vietnam.

Literature Review

Job performance (JP)

A highly effective employee can complete assigned tasks correctly and entirely with optimal results compared with previously determined standards (Krijgsheld et al., 2022; Roy et al., 2023). The authors focused on two primary levels at which role behaviours contribute to work results, individual and group, and three different types of behaviour: (1) task performance, (2) contextual performance, and (3) adaptive performance. In addition, measurable work results and predictive or critical standards specified in a framework are tools to evaluate the effectiveness of individuals, groups, and organisations (Yiming et al., 2024; Park et al., 2022). This concept has been developed and agreed upon by several researchers. It

is a multidimensional variable with at least two dimensions: task and contextual performance. In this study, the authors focused on two main aspects of work results: task and contextual performance.

Task performance (TP)

Task performance is built with three attributes: (1) specific job qualifications, (2) written and oral communication, and (3) supervision, in the case of leadership, and one part of management/administration (Adekiya, 2024). Thus, task performance includes meeting company goals and making effective sales presentations that vary across jobs within the same organization. Task performance outcomes also directly or indirectly contribute to individual and organisational performance (Elamalki et al., 2024).

Contextual performance (CP)

Contextual performance is defined as an employee's behaviour based on a task with an element of contingency outside the employee's usual tasks, which is believed to directly promote effective performance without directly affecting employee productivity (Sypniewska et al., 2023; Elamalki et al., 2023). This indirectly contributes to the functioning of an organization by facilitating task performance. Studies have listed five types of contextual work outcomes: (1) volunteering for activities beyond one's formal job requirements, (2) enthusiasm to complete essential tasks, and (3) following rules and prescribed procedures even when it is inconvenient and publicly defending the organisation's goals.

Theoretical Framework

Knowledge (KN), Task Performance (TP), Job Performance (JP), and Contextual Performance (CP)

Knowledge is an essential intangible asset in corporations. Effective companies are typically characterised by a culture of continuous learning in which all employees consistently acquire, generate, and disseminate knowledge among their colleagues (Yiming et al., 2024). Knowledge is the most precious asset and a crucial resource for enterprises. Knowledge is vital for a firm to preserve its competitive edge and is an essential catalyst for an organisation's significance (Demir et al., 2023). Knowledge is assessed from several perspectives, including an employee's existing knowledge, knowledge dissemination to others, and the cumulative information they have acquired. Accumulated from colleagues/experiences in the learning process and proposed H1, H2, and H3 in Figure 1.

Attitude (AT), Task Performance (TP), Job Performance (JP), and Contextual Performance (CP)

Attitude can be understood as an emotional state expressed in human behaviour. They make statements, comments, and judgments and react to the world through gestures, speech, actions, gestures, and facial expressions (Shepherd et al., 2021). Additional research indicates that employees possess specific motivations, such as empathy and the capacity to anticipate needs. Personality traits have been hypothesised to affect how individuals handle work-related situations. Another study proposed that the personality traits of an agreeable, warm, and caring person are likely to enhance job performance. Likewise, each employee's positive attitude impacts service delivery, which meets customer expectations, and proposes a scale for attitude variables through liking for job performance, job compatibility, and understanding/empathy and proposes H4, H5, and H6 in Figure 1

Hard skills (HS), Task Performance (TP), Job Performance (JP), and Contextual Performance (CP)

Hard skills can be broadly defined and are contingent on the particular situation in which they are applied. Hard skills encompass the technical components of job tasks and typically include information acquisition. These abilities are predominantly technical and frequently include tools such as project planning (Duan et al., 2023; Ybema et al., 2020). Based on the above concepts, other studies have suggested ways to measure hard skills, including (a) proficiency in using essential technical software at work, (b) proficiency in using related tools to work, and (c) the ability to learn and find information related to the work field and proposed H7, H8, and H9 Figure 1.

Soft skills (SS), Task Performance (TP), Job Performance (JP), and Contextual Performance (CP)

Soft skills are communication, people, and behavioural skills necessary to apply technical and workplace knowledge. Soft skills include skills, abilities, and characteristics related to personality, attitude, and behaviour rather than formal or technical knowledge. Other studies have examined soft skills as intrinsic abilities encompassing self-management and interpersonal skills, which involve effectively navigating social interactions (Deng et al., 2023). As a result, soft skills are largely intangible, unrelated to deliverables or actual output, and are utilised without tools or templates and are proposed in H10, H11, and H12 Figure 1.

Technology (TE), Task Performance (TP), Job Performance (JP), and Contextual Performance (CP)

Assessing employees' digital capabilities is an essential part of the human resource management process in the banking industry, especially during the digital transformation process. (Kisekka & Goel, 2023). Communication and collaboration are based on the proficiency to engage, communicate, and cooperate with others using digital technologies while considering cultural and generational differences, managing one's digital identity and online reputation, and participating in social networks through public and private digital platforms. Digital content production involves the capacity to generate, change, and enhance digital materials while adhering to licenses and copyrights and proposed H13, H14, and H15 Figure 1.

Task Performance (TP), Job Performance (JP), and Contextual Performance (CP)

Previous studies have found that task-specific job performance influences overall job performance. Inheriting previous research, studies have also proven that evaluating work results through contextual and task-based work results is more effective (Deng et al., 2023; Kumari & Kumar, 2023). Therefore, contextual and task-based work results serve as intermediary variables in this study to help the authors better assess the overall work results of employees in the banking sector (Ringle et al., 2020). Thus, the authors proposed hypotheses H16 and H17 Figure 1.

The authors chose to investigate five factors adjusted to impact career competency on employees' job performance in commercial banks. Specifically, the research model is as follows in Figure 1 follows:

Source: The authors proposed the model

Figure 1: A research model for critical factors influencing employees’ job performance at commercial banks in Vietnam

Figure 1 depicts five critical factors of career competency on employees’ job performance in commercial banks in Vietnam, with essential factors such as (1) knowledge, (2) attitude, (3) hard skills, (4) soft skills, and (5) technology. Dependent variable: Employees’ job performance is evaluated based on three criteria: (1) job performance, (2) task performance, and (3) contextual performance. Therefore, career competency should be considered a significant factor affecting the job performance of banking sector employees.

Research Methods

To conduct the research, the authors built a research process in Figure 2 that included the following steps: (1) Raise the problem and make a theoretical basis. Based on the importance and urgency of the topic, the authors synthesised theories related to the topic as a theoretical basis for the research (Hair et al., 2018). Review-related research works to develop a basis for this topic. (2) Draft scale: After discussions with 15 managers at 15 commercial banks, the authors synthesised opinions and suggestions and completed the scale used for research. (3) Qualitative research: The authors interviewed experts on a draft scale. After synthesizing opinions, suggestions, and adjustments, many respondents tested the scale to re-evaluate it. After the adjustment, it became the official scale. (4) Quantitative research: The content of the official scale was surveyed according to the selected sample size. Survey data were analyzed using the following steps. Qualitative research aims to check the clarity of words, evaluate the accuracy of the meaning of each statement, identify new factors, and apply the following steps.

Step 1: The authors reviewed the theory, built a theoretical framework based on this theory, interviewed 15 managers from directors, evaluated criteria, and identified factors impacting career competency on employees’ job performance in commercial banks (Hair et al., 2018). A total of 15 managers were asked, with 86.67% thinking the questionnaire was straightforward and easy to understand, 13.33% believed that the questionnaire was too long to answer, some spelling and writing errors needed to be corrected, and the 5-point Likert scale should be evaluated more clearly and in detail for each category. All respondents' feedback was recorded so the questionnaire could be adjusted to suit their current situation. However, the 5-point Likert-based scale was maintained because it is based on previous surveys and is convenient for data analysis.

Step 2: Build a scale and draft the questionnaire and the preliminary survey process. This step built a scale to evaluate the level of factors of career competency on employees’ job performance in commercial banks in Vietnam, with essential factors such as (1) knowledge, (2) attitude, (3) hard skills, (4) soft skills, and (5) technology. Dependent variable: Employees’ job performance is evaluated based on three criteria: (1) job performance, (2) task performance, and (3) contextual performance. Before sample collection, preliminary research was conducted to reduce the number of unreliable observed variables. The questionnaire included 27 main content items for the research focus. 150 survey forms were sent to 15 bank branches for a preliminary survey. After eliminating invalid samples, 135 samples were used for initial research. The results showed that all scales were considered satisfactory. Based on the comments of 15 bank managers, the questionnaire was adjusted, completed, and sent to the employees.

Step 3: After revising the questionnaire, we surveyed significant commercial banks in six Southeast provinces: Ho Chi Minh City, Dong Nai Province, Binh Duong, Binh Phuoc, Tay Ninh, and Ba Ria-Vung Tau. Furthermore, the writers personally examined 900 survey votes from 40 branches of 15 Vietnamese commercial banks, each province and city estimated to have 150 staff. Respondents received surveys by email and phone. Online forms for the survey were accessible at the 40 branches from January to June 2024.

Step 4: The questionnaire was cleaned and put into data processing software. Descriptive statistical data combined with qualitative and quantitative analysis to explore how career competency affects job performance at Vietnamese commercial banks. Hair et al. (2018) determined the sample size based on the processing technique for Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.7, EFA, SEM, and measured model fit with $GFI \geq 0.900$, $TLI \geq 0.900$, $CFI \geq 0.900$, and $RMSEA < 0.1$. The above bank branch employees were surveyed by email using random convenience sampling.

Results

Testing key factors affecting employees’ job performance at commercial banks in Vietnam

Table 1: Testing of Cronbach's alpha for factors affecting employees’ job performance at commercial banks in Vietnam

Items	Cronbach's alpha	Mean	Std. Deviation
Knowledge (KN)	0.924	3.028	0.998
Attitudes (AT)	0.908	3.026	0.984
Hard skills (HS)	0.938	3.051	1.003
Soft skills (SS)	0.897	3.306	0.986
Technology (TE)	0.856	3.400	0.930
Task performance (TP)	0.879	3.295	0.994
Job performance (JP)	0.830	2.374	0.659
Contextual performance (CP)	0.879	3.289	0.998

Source: own calculations in SPSS 20.0.

Table 1 shows that Cronbach’s alpha value for employees’ job performance was 0.830–0.879. This result confirms that the scale ensures reliability with a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.7, as shown, and the correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). To test the scale's reliability, the authors presented the research process and data collected from 850 employees in the banking sector.

Table 2: Testing SEM model for factors affecting employees’ job performance

Relationships			Standardized Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	SE-Bias	Hypothesis	Result
KN	→	CP	0.574	0.032	15.876	***	0.001	H1	Accepted
AT	→	CP	0.086	0.025	2.811	0.005	0.002	H4	Accepted
HS	→	CP	0.094	0.023	3.197	0.001	0.004	H7	Accepted
SS	→	CP	0.057	0.032	2.689	0.007	0.003	H10	Accepted
TE	→	CP	0.156	0.030	4.910	***	0.004	H13	Accepted
KN	→	TP	0.223	0.033	6.060	***	0.002	H2	Accepted
AT	→	TP	0.088	0.029	2.448	0.014	0.004	H5	Accepted
HS	→	TP	0.111	0.028	3.190	0.001	0.004	H8	Accepted
SS	→	TP	0.052	0.038	2.123	0.034	0.003	H11	Accepted
TE	→	TP	0.138	0.035	3.746	***	0.003	H14	Accepted
KN	→	JP	0.298	0.024	6.806	***	0.001	H3	Accepted
AT	→	JP	0.086	0.017	2.610	0.009	0.003	H6	Accepted
HS	→	JP	0.073	0.016	2.351	0.019	0.001	H9	Accepted
SS	→	JP	0.050	0.021	2.246	0.025	0.005	H12	Accepted
TE	→	JP	0.093	0.020	2.767	0.006	0.001	H15	Accepted
TP	→	JP	0.060	0.021	1.770	0.077	0.001	H16	Accepted
CP	→	JP	0.345	0.028	7.675	***	0.001	H17	Accepted

*Source: Authors collected and processed from SPSS 20.0, Amos, Note *** significance at 0.01.*

Table 2 indicates the significance level of 0.05 for the critical components of career competency on employees’ job performance in commercial banks in Vietnam, with essential elements such as (1) knowledge, (2) attitude, (3) hard skills, (4) soft skills, and (5) technology. In addition, contextual and task performance as mediators based on indirect influence through contextual performance (CP) were significantly influenced by KN (0.574), TE (0.156), HS (0.094), AT (0.086), and SS (0.057). As demonstrated in Table 2, the variables influencing employees’ job performance at commercial banks were investigated through Bootstrap testing with 60.000 samples, with a significance level of 0.05 (C.R. < 1.96). This outcome is in complete harmony with the principles of employees’ job performance at commercial banks. This finding provides scientific evidence that policymakers can utilise to inform their predictions.

Source: Authors collected and processed from SPSS 20.0, Amos

Figure 3: Testing SEM for factors affecting employees’ job performance at commercial banks

Figure 3 depicts the significance threshold 0.01 for assessing five essential components of employees’ job performance in commercial banks in Vietnam. The following statistical metrics measured the model's fit: GFI = 0.931 (>0.900), TLI = 0.957 (>0.900), CFI = 0.965 (> 0.900), and RMSEA = 0.049 (< 0.1) in Figure 3. According to the data presented above, research model testing showed that five critical factors of career competency on employees’ job performance of commercial banks in Vietnam, with essential elements such as (1) knowledge, (2) attitude, (3) hard skills, (4) soft skills and (5) technology.

Discussion of findings

The findings derived from the structural equation modelling (SEM) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) provide significant insights into the multifaceted determinants of employees’ job performance in Vietnam's commercial banking sector. The relationships explored across dimensions of task performance, contextual performance, and overall job performance highlight critical drivers of employee effectiveness.

Knowledge emerged as a pivotal determinant, with a standardised estimate of 0.574, indicating a robust and positive influence on contextual performance (Yiming et al., 2024; Demir et al., 2023). This underscores the essential role of a comprehensive knowledge base in facilitating task-specific outcomes and broader organizational contributions. (2) Attitude was identified as another critical factor,

significantly impacting task and contextual performance, with standardised estimates of 0.088 and 0.086, respectively (Shepherd et al., 2021). Positive employee attitudes are associated with heightened engagement, resilience, and alignment with organizational objectives.

Based on the standardised estimate of 0.094 on contextual performance, hard skills reinforce their instrumental role in enabling employees to execute technical and operational tasks precisely (Duan et al., 2023). These skills are particularly crucial in digital transformation, where proficiency in technology and analytical tools enhances operational efficiency and compliance with evolving industry standards. Although contributing more modestly based on the standardised estimate of 0.057, soft skills remain indispensable for fostering interpersonal collaboration and adaptability in an evolving work environment (Luo et al., 2021; Shepherd et al., 2021). Effective communication, conflict resolution, and teamwork are vital for sustaining organizational cohesion and innovation, especially in sectors reliant on client interaction and service delivery.

The role of technological competency was significantly highlighted, particularly in its influence on contextual performance based on the standardised estimate of 0.156 (Duan et al., 2023; Kisekka & Goel, 2023). This finding accentuates the imperative for digital literacy and innovation within the banking sector, aligning with global trends towards technology-driven service enhancements. The study further identified a strong correlation between contextual and overall job performance based on the standardised estimate of 0.345 (Sypniewska et al., 2023). Employees who excel in roles requiring initiative, collaboration, and adaptability are likelier to exhibit comprehensive effectiveness, underscoring the need for integrative competency development frameworks that address technical and contextual dimensions.

Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

Conclusions

Based on testing the structural equation model consisting of five factors: knowledge, attitude, hard skills, soft skills, and technology, and examining the impact of the above factors on tasks, context, and job performance from 900 employees working for commercial banks in Vietnam and processed using SPSS 20.0 and Amos software. The research results show that employees with better professional competencies have higher task-based work results than context-based ones. Finally, the study also evaluated the results achieved, qualitatively and quantitatively analyzed the influencing factors, and pointed out shortcomings and limitations that require specific recommendations to enhance them in the future. Improving and enhancing employee work results helps managers re-evaluate employees' work progress and is also a premise for the overall development of the entire organization. Improving work results also allows employees to learn and develop more at work. Therefore, managers should regularly evaluate employees in an organization. Finally, there are five proposed priority policy implications for career competency on employees' job performance in commercial banks in Vietnam.

Policy Recommendations

To improve job performance, managers should prioritise cultivating contextual behaviours, enhancing employees' knowledge and technical skills, fostering a supportive and engaging work environment, and proposing five policy implications for employee job performance in Vietnam.

(1) Improved knowledge (KN) based on standardised estimate is 0.574 with sig. 0.0001 in Table 2. Therefore, commercial banks should continue their training and human resource development. Banks

need to focus on improving the quality of training and fostering and developing human resources, considering this a pivotal task in raising the staff level to meet the requirements of the new era. Accordingly, banks must develop a clear training roadmap and commit to following it, particularly training programs for leadership, planning, and pre-appointment staff. The retraining of officials and employees must be conducted regularly. Training materials and necessary information for the banking business necessitate extra training in legal and technical understanding, sales expertise, managerial acumen, and communication proficiency.

(2) Improve technology (TE) based on standardised estimate is 0.156 with sig. 0.0001 in Table 2. Therefore, commercial banks should enhance training and foster practical capacity in commercial banks by building and implementing a human resource rotation mechanism between units and systems throughout the industry. The State Bank will be the focal point for implementing the rotation and secondment of staff between the State Bank and commercial banks and between the State Bank, commercial banks, and training schools. Each commercial bank is encouraged to build an internal rotation mechanism so the staff can understand many job positions, expand their horizons, and improve their ability to coordinate effectively at work. Third, the capacity and quality of training facilities in the industry, including training facilities under the State Bank of Vietnam in the national education system, training schools, and training centres of banks.

(3) Improved hard skills (HS) based on standardised estimate is 0.094 with sig. 0.001 in Table 2. Training policies and programs should be developed to improve employee performance, motivation, and job satisfaction. This increases employee loyalty and commitment to their organisation and ultimately assists organisations in achieving their strategic goals, vision, and mission. Training programs must provide employees with a sustainable learning path, helping them continuously learn systematically and improve even after joining the organisation. Third, there is a plan for training and fostering workers to improve their professional qualifications and working techniques in the direction of deep expertise and proficient application of modern technology.

(4) Improve attitudes (AT) based on the standardised estimate of 0.086 with sig. 0.005 in Table 2. Therefore, employee attitudes play a vital role in improving organizational productivity. By incorporating personality development programs such as role-plays, group discussions, and business games, superior and subordinate relationships can be strengthened. Banks should conduct training courses so employees feel that training is necessary to improve productivity and customer satisfaction, and meet new business challenges. At the same time, banks should regularly review and improve working conditions, compensation, and benefits to retain talented staff because these employees are always attractive to organisations. It would be great if all the employees in the bank were always full of energy and devoted to their work. However, the sad truth is that it rarely occurs because employee attitudes decline over time without any interaction from the bank.

(5) Improved soft skills (SS) based on standardised estimate is 0.057 with sig. 0.007 in Table 2. Consequently, the work efficiency of the entire enterprise is reduced. This is why soft skills training programs for internal personnel are receiving much attention from business owners. With expertise and soft skills, employees complete tasks more quickly and effectively. Four ways to strengthen employees'

soft skills through e-learning. First, online group collaboration enhances teamwork skills. Online team collaboration projects directly affect employees' problem-solving, communication, and creative thinking skills. Through this activity, they work together to reach a consensus and effectively find solutions. Second, we weave real-life situations into the e-learning lectures. Real-life situations are interactive methods that require learners to have consistent perceptions, behaviors, and attitudes.

Limitations and future research: Five core competency dimensions, knowledge, attitude, hard skills, soft skills, and technology, were examined to assess job performance. However, company culture, leadership style, and external economic situations may affect employee performance but were not considered in the model. These variables should be considered in future research to improve understanding. Self-assessment surveys may bring social desirability and self-perception biases. The results may be less reliable without peer or supervisor reviews, notwithstanding accuracy measures. Multi-source feedback may improve data dependability in future investigations. Thus, technological adaptations are based on rapid technological advancements, and future research should refine the technological competency scale to include emerging areas like artificial intelligence, blockchain, and big data analytics, which are increasingly relevant in banking. Mixed-method evaluations, such as interviews and focus groups, can supplement quantitative findings.

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